

Fatty Acids

1. Heptynyl -6-malonic acid
2. Octadecatrienoic acid
3. Pentanoic acid
4. Butanoic acid

Methyl Esters

1. Thiosulfuric acid 2-amino methyl ester
2. Oxirane pentanoic acid-3 undecyl methyl ester
3. Trioxalane octanoic acid methyl ester
4. Cyclopropane butanoic acid methyl ester
5. Octadecatrienoic acid methyl ester

Supplementary Table S1. Profile description of sarcin, thionin, chitinase and its derivatives of *Aspergillus giganteus*

Selected derivatives	Compound	PubChem ID	Molecular Weight	Log P	Rotatable bonds	Acceptors	Donors	Surface area
Standard Drug	Fluconazole	3365	306.276	0.7358	5	7	1	123.419
Sarcin	1-Methylthioguianine	3032391	181.224	0.60809	0	5	2	73.255
	3-Imino-3H-phenothiazin-7-amine	65044	227.292	2.46277	0	4	2	96.045
Thionin	Thionine cation	462371	228.3	0.6431	0	3	2	96.045
	3-Methyl-2-[[[(8E)-7-methylidene-5-(trifluoromethyl)-3,4,5,6-tetrahydro-2H-thionin-8-yl]methyl]-7-(4-methylimidazol-1-yl)-3,4-dihydropyrido[1,2-a]pyrazine-1,6-dione	122678533	492.567	4.72242	3	6	0	199.708
	N,N-Dimethyl-4-[(Z)-[(3Z,6Z,8Z)-2H-thionin-5-ylidene]methyl]aniline	88094842	269.413	4.5089	2	2	0	119.564
Chitinase	Chitinase-IN-2	86223064	395.488	2.45152	6	7	1	166.525
	Chitinase-IN-1	86223063	352.419	2.38552	5	6	1	148.035
	Chitin from Shrimp cells	6857375	221.209	-3.0776	2	6	5	86.290